

Co-Creating Snacks: A Cross-Cultural Study with Mediterranean Children within the DELICIOUS Project

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Abstract: Mediterranean Diet adherence has been decreasing during the last decades, and non-appropriate snacking habits have also been identified among Mediterranean children and adolescents. To co-create new snacks, as well as to explore children's interests and preferences, a multi-method approach was used in the present study, including some qualitative and quantitative research phases. Conducted in collaboration with schools in Lebanon, Egypt, Portugal, Italy, and Spain, different snack prototypes were designed and tested in a Mediterranean cross-cultural context. Results showed significant differences among countries in snacking preferences and general food-related attitudes. Italian children exhibited higher levels of neophobia, resulting in lower acceptance of all proposed snacks. Some sensory and contextual insights were collected such as Egyptian children favoring sweet and crunchy textures, or "At school", "With my friends," and "As a morning/afternoon snack", being identified as linked to snacks acceptance in some countries. The present study underscores the value of co-creation processes involving children to address non-recommended dietary patterns, highlighting the critical role of sensory properties, cultural differences, and contextual factors to designing healthy snacks that meet the Mediterranean Diet principles but are highly appreciated by the young population segments. 19

Keywords: Co-design; consumer study; sensory properties; emojis; acceptance. 20

Citation: To be added by editorial staff during production. 21

Academic Editor(s): 22

Received: date 23

Accepted: date 24

Published: date 25

Publisher's Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations. 26

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1. Introduction 28

The Mediterranean diet has (MD) been suggested as an example of a healthy diet for decades, and therefore promoted due to its cardioprotective and beneficial effects [1]. Because food choices have been reported to be shaped early in life [2], several nutritional programs have been designed and launched to investigate and increase MD adherence among children [3-6]. In general, high levels of physical activity and meal frequency, low screen time, and low scores on external-eating-behavior have been associated with higher adherence to the Mediterranean diet [4]. Besides identifying deviations from MD in general dietary patterns, some of the key findings from these studies have shown that participants' snacking behaviors often diverged from the recommended MD guidelines, with 29

children and adolescents often consuming fruits and vegetables, but also sugared beverages and different kinds of processed snacks (candies and salty snacks) [7,8].

Adherence to an unhealthy snacking pattern has been associated with a greater incidence of metabolic syndrome [9], suggesting that the quality of snacks, rather than simply their frequency, could play a crucial role in disease risk. Some hypotheses have been proposed to explain the shift on the current snacking habits among children. Fernández San Juan [7] reported that Spanish children's growing independence was contributing to a shift away from traditional MD and towards unhealthy snacking habits, choosing processed foods with lower nutritional value. In addition, the external-eating-profile has been positively associated with the frequency of consumption of snack-food among children [10], besides its aforementioned negative correlation with MD adherence [4]. External-eaters are those who eat mainly driven by external stimuli, such as the mere presence of the food or its smell [11]. Therefore, promoting healthy snacking is crucial for reintroducing Mediterranean diet principles to young people, and increasing nutritious snack options could be a strategy to encourage external eaters to make healthier choices.

The concept of co-creation has gained traction in the field of food design, recognizing the value of actively engaging with consumers to gather their opinions, expectations, and beliefs throughout different phases (e.g.: idea generation) of new product development process [12,13]. Galler et al. [14,15] explored the feasibility of including preadolescents to cocreate healthy snacks, proposing a series of activities in which the young participants could propose new product ideas, while researchers collected not only these ideas, but additional insights linked to the psychosocial aspects of snacking. Besides this approach for food design, codesign and cocreation activities with children have been proposed to develop new games [16], outdoor play activities [17] and even a health report card [18]. Jenkins et al. [19] proposed co-design activities with adolescents to create new recipes from leftovers. These authors reported that adolescents not only enjoyed the intervention process, but also developed a deeper understanding of the issue of food waste and its environmental implications, highlighting the potential of the research process as a learning-by-doing activity.

The aim of the present study was to deploy a cocreation activity in which children from different Mediterranean countries could express their opinions and ideas about different kinds of snacks to develop alternatives to the low-nutritional quality ones they were currently consuming. Results from the descriptive analysis on Mediterranean diet adherence of the children involved in the project (DELICIOUS) [20] indicated that only a minority of participants fulfilled the positive recommendation of "daily consumption of pasta, cereals, and nuts" from the KIDMED questionnaire, and suggested inadequate consumption of fruits and vegetables, as well as sweets and candies [21]. Therefore, the aim was to develop products in which some of these ingredients were included (e.g.: nuts, cereals), trying to promote healthier snacking among Mediterranean children. In addition, results of this study indicated that products most consumed by children who take a snack were fruit (26%), and commercial biscuits and pastries (21%). Because fruits are perfect snacks that should not be replaced, the "commercial biscuits and pastries" category was the main target for improvement, with the aim of providing attractive substitutes for the products available on the market.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study protocol

The present study was conducted within the context of the European-funded DELICIOUS project, which study protocol has been recently described [20] and approved by the ethics committee of Mondragon University (no. IEB-20230704).

2.2. General procedure and methodology

The co-creation process proposed in the present study consisted of a multi-method approach in which 5 different stages were planned with different points of interaction with children and/or their caregivers.

Qualitative Data Collection: This phase involved conducting study trips to the different countries (Portugal, Spain, Italy, Egypt, Lebanon), in which researchers explored the local environments, market dynamics, and visited different schools. The study trips included conducting interviews with caregivers (teachers, canteen staff and cooks, and parents) to have a general idea on children's needs, preferences, and challenges in food related childcare. During the interviews, researchers collected qualitative information on the typical snacks consumed by children as well as snacking moments. Interviews were conducted by two researchers; notes were taken and later discussed to extract some highlights from each country. The main objectives of these trips and interviews were 1) to identify foods that were less accepted by children, as well as which ones they liked the most (considering the traditional local cuisine), 2) to determine mealtimes/number of meals at home vs school, as well as snacking habits, 3) to get a general idea on children behavior and participation in tasks such as buying food, cooking, tidying up and cleaning the kitchen/dining room, etc.

Prototype Design and Development: Based on the comprehensive insights gathered during the data collection phase, initial product prototypes were developed by the research team (composed of chefs and food scientists). These prototypes were mainly designed to explore children perception during the next cocreation phase. The aim of this stage was to create tangible versions of food products that could be made in real-world scenarios, using a variety of ingredients (nuts, eggs, vegetables, cereals, seeds, cheese, chocolate) and resulting in a wide range of flavors and textures (salty, sweet, crunchy, soft, etc.), allowing children to interact with different kinds of stimuli and making processes. Six different product prototypes were formulated to be later used in the hands-on-activity (Table 1).

Feedback on Prototypes: Hands-on Activity. Researchers directly engaged with children through co-creation/cooking sessions, exploring their opinions, reactions, attitudes, and user experiences during the snack making process. Two workshops were conducted in each country, with 9-12 children/adolescents from 9-14 years old participating in each of them (n total > 100). During the sessions, the team composed by a chef and a researcher 1) introduced the aim of the workshop, 2) discussed with children the different aspects of Mediterranean Diet, 3) talked about their general preferences and food related habits, and 4) children were given guidance in cooking the 6 different snacks. Once all snacks were ready, 5) children participated in a tasting activity in which the products were assessed using emojis (each participant had a 11-emojis set to be used as a Check-All-That-Apply judgment) [22]. Finally, to determine children's opinion about the co-creation/cooking workshop, 6) the whole activity was also assessed using the emojis-set. Each session lasted approximately 120 min.

Table 1. Ingredient composition of the different prototypes used during the hands-on activity with children.

Oat muffins		Sesame tahini cookies		Carrot cake bliss balls	
%	Ingredient	%	Ingredient	%	Ingredient
41%	Mascarpone cheese	35%	Almond flour	29%	Sunflower seeds
20%	Eggs	26%	Honey	29%	Shredded coconut
12%	Oatmeal flakes	18%	Sesame seeds	25.4%	Dates
9.8%	Cashews	18%	Tahini	13%	Carrots
9.8%	Dark chocolate chunks	1%	Vanilla extract	2%	Maple syrup
6%	Cane sugar	0.7%	Baking soda	1%	Salt
1.3%	Baking Powder	1%	Sea salt	0.6%	Cinnamon
0.5%	Salt				
Carrot cake		Seed crackers		Honey granola bar	
%	Ingredient	%	Ingredient	%	Ingredient
25.6%	Carrot	56.5%	Water	26.4%	Oatmeal flakes
22%	All-purpose flour	12.4%	Pumpkin seeds	23.3%	Hazelnuts
15%	Eggs	12.4%	Sesame seeds	13.2%	Dried fruit mix
14.5%	Brown sugar	5.6%	Chia seeds	13%	Honey
12.8%	Vegetable oil	4.5%	Poppy seeds	9%	Butter
9.2%	Hazelnuts	4.5%	Flax seeds	6.3%	Dark brown sugar
0.2%	Salt	2.3%	Oatmeal	6.3%	Sunflower seeds
0.2%	Cinnamon & nutmeg	1%	Salt	1%	Salt
0.2%	Vanilla extract	0.4%	Cumin	1%	Vanilla extract
0.15%	Baking powder	0.4%	Garlic powder	0.5%	Cinnamon
0.15%	Baking soda				

Prototype Optimization: Considering results from the previous phase, one of the prototypes was selected (granola bars), refined, and different flavor options were proposed. The children's opinions and reactions collected on the previous phase guided improvements, with an emphasis on enhancing the product's appeal and functionality. The prototype was scaled to industrial level and, therefore, some of the corrections were made to allow the industrialization process. Table 2 shows the general recipe of the granola bars formulated and selected for the last stage of product development, the cross-cultural assessment. Five different recipes with different nuts and dried fruits were developed considering the product base, with the aim of testing several flavor combinations: 1) orange and almonds (OA), 2) peach and walnuts (PW), 3) raisins and walnuts (RW), 4) sesame seeds and dates (SD), and 5) apple with walnuts (AW).

Table 2. Ingredient composition of the different prototypes used during the hands-on activity with children.

%	Ingredient	Detail on ingredients
12-19%	Nuts	Hazelnuts, walnuts, almond
18%	Cereals	Oat, sorghum, quinoa, rice
12-17%	Seeds	Pumpkin, sunflower, sesame
16%	Honey	
11%	Butter (unsalted)	
9%	Dried fruit	Peach, dates, orange, apple, raisins
7%	Brown sugar	
5%	Chocolate cover	>70% cocoa
2%	Olive pulp extract	
1%	Salt and spices	Cinnamon, vanilla extract

Final Product Assessment: Cross-cultural Study. This stage involved analyzing the five distinct versions of the product, each of them incorporating distinctive ingredients. A comparative study was conducted to determine acceptance using a 7-emojis scale appropriate for children and for the cross-cultural context [23]; in addition, a Check-All-That-Apply question including different terms collected during the Hands-On activity (ingredients, emotions, consumption contexts) was incorporated in the questionnaire to assess how children perceived each snack version. Over 450 children participated in the tasting study. After removing incomplete questionnaires, a total of 425 responses from the different countries were gathered (participation rate: 23,5 % from Egypt, 11,1 % from Italy, 17,9% from Lebanon, 30,4% from Portugal and 17,2 % from Spain; 54% belonging to the 6-12 years old group, and 46% belonging to the 13-17 years old group).

To decide on the specific tasting procedure, researchers responsible of conducting the snacks tasting in each country discussed two possibilities: a) a real-context scenario in which each child received a bar during a school day, tasted it whenever hungry/wanted to eat it, and then answered the corresponding questionnaire -each snack version had to be tested on a different day-; or, b) a controlled setting where pieces of the snack samples were monadically served in a classroom, and children completed the questionnaire. The second option was selected and, therefore, the consumer testing could be considered a central-location test. Samples were coded and randomized for serving.

2.3. Data analysis

Qualitative data collected during the study trips, as well as the notes on comments and general behavior of children during the hands-on activity, was gathered by researchers and then discussed in working sessions to extract the main information, highlights and differences among countries. Data about the emojis activity conducted during the hands-on session with children was treated as a Check-All-That-Apply question. Two contingency tables were built with the data "Country/Emoji" and "Snack/Emoji", and Fisher's Exact tests were conducted to explore significant differences among countries and snacks. In addition, two Correspondence Analyses were done to explore relationships among variables. Data from the cross-cultural consumer test on the five final granola bars was analyzed by two-ways ANOVA considering sample, country, and their interaction, as factors. Differences were considered significant when $p < 0.05$, unless otherwise stated. All statistical analyses were done using XLStat (Version, 2021.5, Addinsoft, USA).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Qualitative research responses

The interviews conducted with children's caregivers (parents, school canteens) during phase one, provided some general ideas which suggested notable differences in snack preferences and snacking habits across countries.

- Snacks chosen by children tended to be from the sweet category, reflecting a cultural preference for sugary options in Portugal.
- In Spain, common snacks included commercial juices and processed sweets, indicating a trend toward convenience-based choices (e.g.: chocolate bars, processed pastries, ready to drink yoghurts).
- Italian children often had access to commercial sweets, packaged sandwiches, and chips, typically available in school kiosks or bars.
- Fresh fruits seemed to be consumed as the primary snack in Egypt, occasionally supplemented by dried fruits such as dates, meaning a more natural and minimally processed snacking habit.
- Lebanese children also seemed to favor fresh products, with snacks often including fruits, contributing to a diet with fewer processed snack items.

In addition, snacking moments also varied across countries, influenced by their unique mealtime patterns; because the definition of a snack is "foods that are eaten in between meals", these differences were foreseeable. These findings from the qualitative phase confirmed the ones obtained during the quantitative study conducted to determine dietary habits on Mediterranean children, in which fruits and commercial biscuits and pastries were the snacks mainly reported by these children's parents [21].

These data were used to formulate the snacks prototypes shown in the Materials and Method section of the present study during phase two of the co-creation process.

Results of the tasting activity, conducted after making the snacks during the hands-on activity (phase three), are included in Figures 1 and 2, which display the correspondence analysis with the emotional responses across different snacks and countries, respectively. Most data variability on the emotional responses elicited by snacks was explained by the first factor (F1), driven by the 😊, 😄, 😞, and 🤢 emojis on the right side, and on the left side. Oat muffins and carrot cake were the snacks eliciting more positive emotions, while tahini cookies, seeds crackers, and honey granola bars seemed to be the products generating less-positive emotions (Figure 1). When asked about potential enhancements to these less-liked snacks, children proposed a range of ingredients and sensory modifications; however, no unifying response was obvious, only "chocolate" seemed to be mentioned by several children as a "flavor enhancer" solution. This response was not surprising because chocolate has been ranked among children's favorite foods in the West cultures and in different societies [24].

Figure 1. Correspondence analysis results showing the emotional responses across different countries (cocreation/cooking workshop).

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Figure 2. Correspondence analysis results showing the emotional responses across different snacks (hands-on activity).

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Interaction with children during the hands-on activity also provided interesting data to identify differences among food-related attitudes in each country. Although all children seemed to be happy to spend their time “cooking snacks”, participants from Portugal,

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Lebanon, and Egypt had a more positive and neophilic attitude to testing new foods, while children in Italy and Spain were more reluctant to try new recipes and ingredients. These impressions were supported by the emojis selected by children to evaluate the snacks (Figure 2), with Portugal, Lebanon, and Egypt predominantly using positive or excited emojis reflecting their openness to trying the snacks, and Italy and Spain often selecting neutral or negative emojis indicating a higher level of reluctance to the snacks. These findings align with the results of previous studies conducted on Italian and Lebanese children [25,26, respectively]. Di Nucci et al. [25] reported a prevalence of intermediate to high levels of food neophobia among Italian children (42.2 ± 14.0), whereas El Mouallem et al. [26] found lower neophobia scores (39.1 ± 8.3) among children in Lebanon, indicating a low to intermediate neophobia profile. The level of neophobia has been reported to be critical for children's adherence to a healthy diet [27] and their acceptance of new snacks [28,29] such as the ones developed for the present study.

In terms of the cooking involvement, some children reported being proactive in assisting their parents with cooking or grocery shopping during the activity, although this was not a general response. The limited participation of children on food and cooking related activities could be attributed to societal shifts toward busier lifestyles, which has been linked to a general decline in culinary skills among the population [30,31], thereby, limiting children's opportunities to develop culinary skills at home.

Engaging children in selecting recipes, purchasing ingredients, and preparing meals has been demonstrated to enhance their willingness to taste novel foods and to positively influence their dietary behaviors [32-34]. By creating familiarity and positive associations, these activities could reduce their hesitance toward less familiar food options. During the hands-on activity conducted in the present research (phase three), all participants were active in processing the different ingredients and making the new snacks, although a small percentage of them did not want to test the final products. Before cooking, the children's initial willingness to try the snacks was notably lower than their final willingness to try them after participating. The results of this intervention reinforced the idea that involving children in hands-on cooking activities increased their willingness to try new products, although a higher participation could be needed to confirm this result, and a follow up control would be needed to determine if children's engagement with food and cooking lasts in time.

3.3. Cross-cultural study: quantitative responses

The results of the two-way ANOVA from the cross-cultural evaluation of the five distinct granola bar versions revealed significant differences in the 7-emojis liking scores across countries and granola bars (p -value < 0.0001). Portuguese, Spanish, Lebanese, and Egyptian children reported similar liking scores for the snacks tested, while Italian children showed significantly lower liking scores for all samples. This finding supports the hypothesis generated during the qualitative phase, which suggested that Italian children were generally more neophobic than their counterparts from other countries. This neophobic tendency was observed during the hands-on activity, where Italian participants were less willing to try the developed snacks (novel recipes or unfamiliar ingredients).

Regarding the granola bars, PW received significantly higher liking scores than RW and AW. These results indicated a clear preference for some of the tested samples, being PW the most liked and AW as the least liked granola bar across all countries. Table 3 shows the results of the one-way ANOVA between granola bars by country, showing cross-cultural differences in samples preferences (the two-ways ANOVA results on the interaction "country x sample" showed significant differences, p -value < 0.0001). PW was one of the most liked granola bars, particularly in Spain. RW stood out as the most favored in Portugal, while SD was the top-rated granola bar in Lebanon and AW was the most liked in Egypt. No significant differences were observed among the granola bars in Italy.

texturally appealing foods, as noted by Birch [35]. Contextual mentions such as "At school" and "With my friends" were linked to the perception of granola bars by both Egyptian (EG) and Spanish (SP) children, emphasizing their appeal in these social settings. This highlights the significant role of peers in shaping children's food choices, particularly in group settings where social influences are highly impactful [36]. Strong positive correlations were observed between attributes such as "Crunchy" and "Nutty," "Sweet" and "Delicious," as well as "At school" and "With my friends", suggesting that these combinations represented favorable sensory and situational perceptions. Attributes such as "Soft," "Fun," and "As a morning/afternoon snack" were more frequently associated with granola bars by children from Portugal (PT) and Lebanon (LB), suggesting their suitability for relaxed or familiar contexts. Sick et al. [37] suggested that emotions elicited by foods in specific contexts could play a crucial role in food acceptance and choice. Therefore, considering the context "As a morning/afternoon snack" could improve the emotional salience of certain granola bars, making them more enjoyable for children.

On the other hand, negative attributes such as "Artificial," "Boring," and "Bad taste" clustered around granola bars tested by children from Italy (IT), highlighting the less favorable perceptions among these young consumers. This finding aligns with previous evidence of higher levels of neophobia among Italian children, likely due to limited exposure to such products [35].

Some of the main limitations of the present study are linked to the lack of characterization on the current background of children participating in the research. Although all settings were similar and specific common guidelines were used to deploy the activities in the different countries, no questionnaires were used to determine the baseline food and cooking related knowledge of children. A pre-selection phase to standardize the population participating in the co-design workshops could be used to improve the proposed methodology and better understand the cross-cultural differences.

5. Conclusions

Co-creation activities with children proved to be effective and insightful for developing healthier snack options that addressed regional preferences. By involving children directly in the creation and evaluation process, different product prototypes were designed to be appealing by children and to improve consumption on specific ingredients typical from the Mediterranean Diet (e.g. nuts, seeds, cereals). Children's snack preferences and general food related attitudes were found to be influenced by a combination of innate sensory predispositions, cultural norms, and contextual factors. Among these, neophobia and familiarity with the product emerged as critical considerations in children's product development. Italian children seemed to exhibit higher levels of neophobia, which resulted in a less favorable perception and lower acceptance of all the developed prototypes. The cross-cultural evaluation of granola bars showed that the peach and walnuts (PW) flavor as the most preferred across countries, highlighting its potential as a healthier alternative to low-nutrition commercial snacks. This study underscores the importance of adapting product development to regional tastes and cultural preferences to maximize acceptance, as well as the value of co-creation in addressing dietary challenges and promoting healthier eating habits among children. Future research should explore the long-term impact of these interventions on dietary adherence, eating behaviors, and health outcomes.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, E.R-A., M.M., and L.V-A.; methodology, E.R-A., M.M., P.B., G.G., and L.V-A.; formal analysis, O.U., M.M.; investigation, E.R-A., M.M., O.U., N.P., N.E-G., R.G., S.P., A.B., and L.V-A.; writing—original draft preparation, E.R-A., M.M., and L.V-A.; writing—review and editing, L.V-A.; supervision, J.P., L.V-A.; funding acquisition, G.G, P.B., J.P., and L.V-A.; project administration, J.P. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Funding: The present research was included in the DELICIOUS project, which has received funding from the PRIMA programme supported by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 2131. The authors acknowledge the participants in the consumer studies for their helpful collaboration.

Data Availability Statement: The data used to support the findings of this study can be made available by the corresponding author upon request.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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